

An Examination of the Relationship between Self-esteem and Imposter Syndrome among College Students

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The interdisciplinary study explored the relationship between self-esteem and imposter syndrome, along with gender differences among college students. It is proposed that self-esteem plays an important role in defining an individual's psychological well-being, and imposter syndrome on the other hand makes a person feels inadequate, and that individual have persistent feelings of self-doubt, distress and being exposed as a fraud which can make an individual unable to recognized one's accomplishments, even when there are signs that an individual is competent and successful, and this can affect anyone, regardless of one's background. The study included a sample of 100 undergraduate students from various departments comprising 50 males and 50 females within the age group 20-25 years from Sazolie College, Kohima, Nagaland. Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES) developed by Rosenberg (1965), revised version (2006), and the Clance Imposter Phenomenon Scale (CIPS) developed by Clance (1985), questionnaires were used to collect data. Statistical analyses, such as descriptive statistics, independent samples t-test, and Pearson's correlation, found a significant negative correlation between self-esteem and imposter syndrome. However, no significant gender differences were observed in either self-esteem or imposter syndrome among participants.

Keywords: Self-esteem, imposter syndrome, Sazolie college students, Kohima, Nagaland

The psychological experiences of college students are molded by various factors such as competitive academic environments, comparison with other people around, personal achievements, feedback from others and the evolving identity structures, where self-esteem and imposter syndrome seem to have emerged as serious determining factors for both academic performance and emotional stability.

Self-esteem, which is an overall evaluation and perception of self-worth and value in psychology, functions as a foundational psychological resource that influences motivation, resilience, and interpersonal functioning of an individual because it shapes a person's attitude, beliefs and behavior (Rosenberg, 1965).

People with high self-esteem tend to view themselves positively with confidence and have adaptive coping strategies, whereas those with low self-esteem tend to have a negative self-image and are more prone to anxiety, self-doubt, and maladaptive thought patterns, where a person can likely avoid opportunities because of not being confident enough, and feeling uncertain about their ability to succeed or overcome challenges (Baumeister et al., 2003).

Whereas, imposter syndrome is a psychological feeling when an individual doubts their own ability and accomplishments and has a persistent fear of being discovered as a fraud, even though there is clear evidence of success, and so such individuals attribute success

to external factors such as luck, timing or situational advantage rather than internal ability (Clance & Imes, 1978).

It is observed that college students in particular are vulnerable to both low self-esteem and imposter syndrome due to various reasons such as academic pressure, social comparison with others, and identity development, etc., which in turn all these experiences can negatively influence academic engagement, mental health, and career development of an individual. Understanding the relationship between self-esteem and imposter syndrome is therefore essential for addressing psychological distress and promoting the academic well-being of an individual.

Theoretical Foundations: Self-esteem and Imposter Syndrome

Self-esteem: Rosenberg's Self-Esteem Theory (1965) emphasizes self-esteem as a universal feeling of self-acceptance and self-worth, with those possessing high self-esteem holding positive assessments of themselves, while those with low self-esteem experience self-doubt and feelings of inadequacy (Rosenberg, 1965).

Imposter Syndrome: The foundational theory of Imposter Syndrome labels the internal experience of self-perceived fraudulence among high-achieving individuals, particularly women (Clance & Imes, 1978). This foundational work proposed that such individuals often attribute their success to luck, effort, or external factors rather than personal ability, leading to persistent feelings of doubt and fear of being exposed as an imposter. This theory emphasized that imposter feelings can lead to chronic anxiety and over-preparation, which in turn reinforces feelings of inadequacy (Clance & Imes, 1978).

Conceptual Link between Self-esteem and Imposter Syndrome

Earlier research findings showed a strong inverse relationship between self-esteem and imposter syndrome, where an individual

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with lower self-esteem is more prone to perfectionism and fear of failure (Kumar & Jagacinski, 2006) which increases the vulnerability to imposter thoughts and can hinder aspects such as career planning, ambition or motivation. Conversely, those with higher self-esteem have greater resilience, as they are more capable of internalizing achievements and viewing challenges as opportunities for growth rather than as threats to self-worth (Neureiter & Traut-Mattausch, 2016). Thus, the relationship is cyclical, where low self-esteem reinforces imposter tendencies, while repeated imposter experiences can further diminish a person's self-esteem.

Review of Literature

Egwurugwu, Ugwuezumba, Ohamaeme, Dike, Eberendu, Egwurugwu, Ohamaeme, and Egwurugwu (2018) conducted a cross-sectional study among 200 undergraduate students, and the study found a significant negative correlation between self-esteem and imposter syndrome, which showed that students with higher self-esteem experienced lower levels of imposter feelings. In the study conducted, the majority of the participants demonstrated high self-esteem and low imposter scores, and no significant gender differences were observed. It is concluded that higher self-esteem acts as a protective factor against imposter syndrome among students.

Mascarenhas, D'Souza, and Bicholkar (2019) conducted a cross-sectional study among 150 students and the results showed that the majority of participants had moderate IP characteristics, followed by participants with high IP characteristics. The study found a moderate negative correlation between imposter phenomenon and self-esteem, indicating that individuals with stronger imposter characteristics had lower self-esteem.

In the study conducted by Naser, Hasan, Zaidi, Mohamed, and Fredericks (2022) the findings showed that 45.2% of the students displayed IP traits, while 18.6% had low self-esteem and found a strong negative correlation between IP and self-esteem, which showed that lower self-esteem significantly predicted higher imposter feelings. Gender and academic year showed no significant differences in IP levels, which suggests that cultural background and self-esteem are key predictors of imposter feelings in diverse academic settings.

In spite of extensive international research, it has been found that limited studies have been conducted in the Indian context, particularly among college students. This gap emphasizes the need for the present study.

Objectives of the Study

- To compare the self-esteem scores of college students based on gender (Male & Female).
- To compare the imposter syndrome of college students based on gender (Male & Female).
- To examine the relationship between self-esteem and imposter syndrome among college students.

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H0*: There will be no significant difference in self-esteem among college students based on gender (Male & Female).
- *H02*: There will be no significant differences in imposter syndrome among college students based on gender (Male &

Female).

- *H03*: There will be no significant relationship between self-esteem and imposter syndrome among college students.

Method

Participants

The target population comprised college-going students of Nagaland enrolled in various departments who voluntarily agreed to participate in the research. The population is diverse in terms of age, gender, and field of study. Participants included both male and female students within the age group of 20-25 years. The total sample size was 100, comprising 50 males and 50 female students, and data was collected from one institution, Sazolie College, Kohima, Nagaland for the study.

Research Design

The present study employed a quantitative, correlational research design to examine the relationship between self-esteem and imposter syndrome among college students.

Measures

Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSES): RSES was developed by Rosenberg in 1965, and is a widely used instrument for measuring global self-worth by assessing both positive and negative feelings about oneself. The scale consists of 10 items rated on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Items 1,3,4,7 and 10 are positively worded, while Items 2,5,6,8 and 9 are negatively worded and therefore reverse-scored and the total score ranges from 10 to 40. High score indicating high self-esteem and Low score indicating low self-esteem. The Scale has a strong construct validity, as supported by its positive correlation with measures of psychological well-being and negative correlation with anxiety and depression. Additionally, the Scale has demonstrated a strong internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha ranging from 0.77 to 0.88, signifying good reliability.

Clance Imposter Phenomenon Scale (CIPS): CIPS was developed by Clance in 1985, which is designed to measure the extent of imposter feelings, including self-doubt, fear of failure, and the inability to internalize success. The scale consists of 20 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from not at all true to very true. Each item is scored from 1 to 5, yielding a total score between 20 and 100. Higher scores indicate stronger imposter feelings, and lower scores indicate fewer imposter experiences. The scale has demonstrated good content and construct validity, consistently correlating with measures of anxiety, self-esteem, and perfectionism, and the Scale has reported reliability coefficients ranging between 0.85 and 0.90, indicating high internal consistency.

Procedure

Data collection procedures adhered to strict ethical standards and necessary permissions were taken from college authorities, and prior consent was obtained from all participants. Data were collected through self-report questionnaires administered to participants and proper instructions were given clearly. The data collection process also ensured strict confidentiality.

Data Analysis

Data examination was performed by using SPSS Version 20.

Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were calculated. To test for gender differences (Objective 1, Objective 2), an independent samples t-test was employed, comparing the mean scores between male and female participants and to determine the direction and strength of the relationship between self-esteem and imposter syndrome (Objective 3), Pearson's Correlation was employed.

Results

Data were analyzed using suitable statistical techniques in accordance with the objectives of the study.

Table 2
Independent Samples Test

Self-esteem	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances			t-test for Equality of Means			
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean difference	Std. error difference
Equal variances assumed	.393	.532	-1.139	98	.257	-1.000	.878
Equal variances not assumed			-1.139	97.579	.257	-1.000	.878

Table 2 determines if the 1.00-point difference found in the first table is statistically significant or just due to chance. Levene's Test for Equality of Variances was considered and the test yielded a value of $F=0.393$ with a significance level of $p = 0.532$. Since this is greater than 0.05, we assume the variances between the two groups are equal. The t-test for equality of means under "equal variances assumed", that t-value is 1.139 with $df = 98$, and the 2-tailed significance (p-value) is 0.257. Because the p-value (0.257) is greater than the standard alpha level of 0.05, the difference in self-esteem between genders (male & female) is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no significant difference in self-esteem based on gender.

Table 4
Independent Samples Test

Imposter syndrome	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances			t-test for Equality of Means			
	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean difference	Std. error difference
Equal variances assumed	.013	.908	1.975	98	.051	5.880	2.977
Equal variances not assumed			1.975	97.967	.051	5.880	2.977

Table 4 examines whether the difference is significant, and independent samples t-test was conducted. Before interpreting the t-test, Levene's test for equality of variances was considered. The Levene's test yielded a value of $F=0.013$ with a significance level of $p=.908$, which is greater than 0.05. This indicated that the assumption of homogeneity of variance is met, and therefore, the

Table 1
Self-esteem (Group statistics) about Males and Females among College Students

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
1 (Female)	50	25.38	4.531	.641
2 (Male)	50	26.38	4.242	.600

Table 1 indicates that for Gender 1 (Female), $N=50$, the mean self-esteem score is 25.38 with a standard deviation of 4.531. For Gender 2 (Male), $N=50$, the mean score is 26.38 with a standard deviation of 4.242, indicating that Gender 2 (Male) participants reported slightly higher levels of self-esteem as compared to Gender 1 (Female) participants.

Table 3
Imposter Syndrome (Group Statistics) about Males and Females among College Students

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
1 (Female)	50	63.12	15.023	2.125
2 (Male)	50	57.24	14.749	2.086

Table 3 Imposter syndrome (Group statistics) indicates that Gender 1 (Female), $N=50$, the mean imposter syndrome score is 63.12 with a standard deviation of 15.023. For Gender 2 (Male), $N=50$, the mean imposter score is 57.24 with a standard deviation of 14.749, indicating that Group 1 participants reported slightly higher levels of imposter syndrome compared to Group 2.

results under "equal variances assumed" are considered. The t-test results showed a t-value of $t=1.975$ with $df=98$ and a significance level of $p=0.051$. Since the p-value is greater than 0.05, the result is not statistically significant at the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no significant difference in imposter syndrome based on gender.

Table 5

Correlations between Self-esteem and Imposter syndrome for the overall Sample

		Self-esteem	Imposter syndrome
Self-esteem	Pearson Correlation	1	-.584
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Imposter Syndrome	Pearson Correlation	-.584	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

Note. **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 5 the relationship between self-esteem and imposter syndrome is found to be significant at the 0.01 level of significance (p value= 0.00; Pearson correlation coefficient=-.584). The relationship is significantly negative, which means that when self-esteem increases, Imposter syndrome decreases. Similarly, if Imposter syndrome increases, Self-esteem decreases. Hence, H_03 is rejected.

Discussion

The present study was conducted to examine the relationship between self-esteem and imposter syndrome among college students, along with gender differences in both variables, and the findings were interpreted based on the suitable statistical technique, including descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation, independent sample test, Levene's test, and t-test.

The findings indicated that the observed difference in self-esteem between the two genders (Male & Female) is not statistically significant, which suggests that gender does not play a significant role in determining self-esteem among the participants, and that both male and female students exhibit comparable levels of self-worth and confidence. Though Male students showed slightly higher mean scores as compared to females, the difference is not statistically meaningful and strong enough to conclude that gender has a significant influence on self-esteem.

It is consistent with previous research findings, such as Teoh (2010) in his study, who found that gender does not significantly affect self-esteem, emphasizing that factors such as personality traits and social support are more important determinants. Another study by Gorrese and Ruggieri (2013) also proved that self-esteem is more strongly influenced by peer attachment, trust, and communication rather than demographic variables such as gender. This indicated that interpersonal relationships and social support systems play a more crucial role in shaping self-esteem.

The findings also suggest that imposter syndrome is experienced by both male and female students at relatively similar levels, and gender does not play a decisive role in determining the presence or intensity of imposter feelings. This indicates that imposter syndrome is not a gender-specific phenomenon but rather a common psychological experience among college students.

In the context of the college environments where students are often exposed to competitive academic settings, high expectations, and constant evaluation, which can contribute to feelings of inadequacy and self-doubt. Both male and female students internalize these pressures in similar ways, leading to comparable levels of imposter syndrome, based on the study findings.

The result can be related to the previous studies such as those by

Ikbaal (2018), who found that there is no significant gender difference in imposter phenomenon among students, and demonstrated that both males and females experience imposterism in similar ways. Likewise, a study conducted by Egwurugwu et al. (2018) also found no significant gender difference in imposter syndrome, suggesting that it is a common psychological experience among students regardless of gender. Another study conducted by Maqsood et al. (2018) also observed that imposter feelings were prevalent among students without a significant difference among gender groups.

Thus, the overall findings showed that imposter syndrome is a common experience among college students, affecting individuals regardless of gender differences. These findings emphasized the need for supportive academic environments and interventions to help students recognize their own abilities, internalize success, and cope effectively with academic and personal challenges.

The third objective of the study, which examines the relationship between self-esteem and imposter syndrome among college students, showed a statistically significant negative relationship between the two variables. It is suggested that as self-esteem increases, imposter syndrome decreases, and conversely, as imposter syndrome increases, self-esteem decreases, which means that students with low self-esteem are more likely to experience higher levels of imposter feelings, whereas students with high self-esteem tend to have fewer imposter experiences.

This relationship suggested that an individual with low self-esteem tends to engage in negative self-evaluation, doubt their own abilities, and attribute their success to external factors such as luck or chance, thereby underpinning feelings of inadequacy and imposterism. On the other hand, individuals with higher self-esteem are more likely to internalize their achievements, maintain confidence in their abilities, and approach academic challenges with a more adaptive and positive mindset, thereby reducing the chance of experiencing imposter feelings.

These findings are also dependable with the previous studies conducted by Egwurugwu et al. (2018) which the study found that there is a significant negative correlation between self-esteem and imposter syndrome, suggesting that students with higher self-esteem experience lower levels of imposter feelings. Another study conducted by Mascarenhas et al. (2019) also found a moderate negative correlation between the two variables, indicating that higher imposter characteristics are associated with lower self-esteem. A study conducted by Naser et al. (2022) also stated a strong negative relationship, which suggested that self-esteem is a key predictor of imposter syndrome.

Studies conducted, such as those by El-Setouhy et al. (2024) also found a significant negative relationship between self-esteem and imposter syndrome. Thus, the findings showed the existence of a cyclical relationship between self-esteem and imposter syndrome, where low self-esteem contributes to the development of imposter syndrome, and repeated experience of imposter feelings further reduces self-esteem and all this can negatively impact students' academic performance, motivation, and psychological well-being, and can lead to increased anxiety, fear of failure, and avoidance of challenges. The moderate levels of self-esteem and the significant negative correlation observed in the study showed that some students may be vulnerable to experiencing imposter feelings, even if they demonstrate adequate competence and ability.

Thus, these findings emphasize the need to focus on enhancing

self-esteem among students as a means of reducing imposter syndrome and promoting psychological well-being, academic confidence, and overall personal development. Therefore, the study provides important insights into the psychological experiences of college students, which highlight the need for supportive academic environments, positive feedback from family, professors and peer support networks and interventions that can promote positive self-evaluation and well-being of the student.

Limitations of the Study

The study is limited only to college students enrolled in undergraduate programs and data is collected only from one College for the study, so the findings will apply only to the sampled population and cannot be generalised to all students.

Recommendations for Next-Stage Interdisciplinary Research

Although the present study provides valuable insights, certain limitations open paths for future research. Future studies and research should include a larger and more diverse sample from different colleges, institutions, and regions and longitudinal studies can also be conducted to examine and understand how self-esteem and imposter syndrome develop and change over time among college students, which would help in understanding the long-term influence on academic performance and mental health. Also, comparative studies across different cultural backgrounds and groups should be conducted to provide deeper insights and cultural factors should be explored in greater detail, especially in the Indian context, as there are only limited empirical findings.

Future research should also focus on developing and testing intervention programs aimed at improving self-esteem and reducing imposter feelings among students, and providing accessible counselling services and effective educational strategies in higher educational settings among college students.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the present study was analysed and interpreted based on the stated objectives. The results showed that there was no significant difference in self-esteem and imposter syndrome among college students on the basis of gender, which suggested that these psychological experiences are not influenced by gender alone, rather it seems to be shaped by broader academic, social, and individual factors.

Additionally, the study showed a significant negative relationship between self-esteem and imposter syndrome, which suggested that students with lower self-esteem are more likely to experience higher levels of imposter feelings and is consistent with previous research findings and highlighted the important role of self-esteem as a protective factor in reducing self-doubt and feelings of inadequacy among college students.

Overall, the findings of the present study showed that though gender may not play a major role, self-esteem is a crucial

psychological factor influencing imposter syndrome among college students, and the results provided an important insight for educators, counsellors, and mental health professionals to design interventions aimed at enhancing self-esteem and reducing imposter feelings, thereby promoting better psychological well-being and academic functioning among college students.

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